

SIMULATION OF REMOTE MONITORING FOR AQUARIUMS

Gabriel Guimarães Moia, Lucas de Biace Torres, Júlia Amorim dos Santos, Victor Franco Godoi and Arnaldo de Carvalho Júnior.

(Instituto Federal de São Paulo, gabriel.moia@ifsp.edu.br, lucas.biace@aluno.ifsp.edu.br, amorim.santos@ifsp.edu.br, victor.franco@ifsp.edu.br, adecarvalhojr@ifsp.edu.br).

Abstract - In this work, we address the simulation of remote monitoring and control of pH, oxygen level, temperature, and luminance in an aquarium. We used the online simulator Wokwi to construct the circuit, and the Blynk app for remote control. The development was carried out in stages, starting with individual tests of sensors integrated with the ESP-32 hardware, followed by the complete integration of the sensors. Some sensors, such as pH and oxygen sensors, needed to be built in the simulator due to the absence of these components in Wokwi. In this context, we present the solutions we found to optimize the functionality of Wokwi when used with Blynk.

Keywords: Remote monitoring; Aquarium simulation; pH control; Blynk app; ESP-32 hardware.

INTRODUCTION

Automation and remote monitoring of systems have become increasingly relevant in various fields, including aquariums. Efficient monitoring of parameters such as pH, oxygen level, temperature, and luminance is essential to ensure the health of the organisms present. With the growing availability of digital tools, utilizing such tools allows us to test and optimize system control without the need for a physical environment, facilitating development and error correction before implementation in a real system [1].

To achieve this, we constructed a simulated circuit using Wokwi [2], an online electronics simulator. To enable remote control, we integrated the system with Blynk, an app that allows communication with programmable hardware, providing an interface for real-time data visualization and control.

In this context, this work proposes the simulation of an automated system for remote monitoring and control in an aquarium using digital tools. Our goal is to develop and test a simulated circuit capable of integrating various sensors, managing data in real time, and allowing users to control the aquatic environment remotely, ensuring ideal conditions for the organisms in a practical and efficient manner.

DEVELOPMENT

Each sensor was integrated with the ESP-32 in isolation to ensure its correct functioning. We developed the code in the Arduino IDE, where we tested each sensor separately to validate data readings.

For the pH and oxygen sensors, since Wokwi does not provide these components, we developed simulations based on pre-existing projects. These sensors were tested to ensure they accurately simulated the typical values of an aquarium environment. The sensors we used included:

A. SERVO MOTOR:

We added a servo motor to automate the feeding of the aquarium, scheduled to occur twice a day, at 6 AM and 6 PM.

Photoelectric Sensor:
 Illuminance level: 500 (lx)

Digital output threshold voltage: 2.5 (Vth)
 LDR resistance: 50 (kilo-ohms)
 Graph slope $\log(R) / \log(Ix)$: 0.7

B. DISSOLVED OXYGEN SENSOR:

The dissolved oxygen sensor, like the pH sensor, does not exist in Wokwi; therefore, we created a custom sensor. Unlike the pH sensor, the selected oxygen sensor for simulation is merely an analog-to-digital converter, with data processing handled via code on the microcontroller itself, as Figure 1.

```
c
#include "wokwi-api.h"
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>

typedef struct {
    pin_t pin;
    float odValue;
} chip_data_t;

void chip_timer_callback(void *data) {
    chip_data_t *chip_data = (chip_data_t *)data;
    float odValue = attr_read(chip_data->odValue);
    float volts = 5 * odValue / 45898;
    pin_dac_write(chip_data->pin, volts);
}

void chip_init() {
    chip_data_t *chip_data = (chip_data_t *)malloc(sizeof(chip_data_t));
    chip_data->odValue = attr_init("odValue", 6410);
    chip_data->pin = pin_init("OUT0", ANALOG);

    const timer_config_t config = {
        .callback = chip_timer_callback,
        .user_data = chip_data,
    };

    timer_t timer_id = timer_init(&config);
    timer_start(timer_id, 1000, true);
}
}
```

Figure 1 – Oxygen Sensor Code.

Dissolved Oxygen Sensor:

Model: SEN0237
 Detection Range: 0–20 mg/L
 Temperature Range: 0–40 °C
 Response Time: Up to 98% complete response within 90 seconds (at 25°C)
 Pressure Range: 0–50 PSI

The data processing is based on a calibration that was not performed since this is a simulation.

C. TEMPERATURE SENSOR:

This sensor was chosen due to the existence of a similar sensor that measures submerged temperature and has extremely similar code.

Model: DS18B20
Measurement Range: -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$
Accuracy: $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ between -10°C and $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$
Temperature Resolution: 9 to 12 bits
Operating Voltage: 3 – 5.5 V
Current Consumption: 1 mA (maximum)
Stainless steel tip

D. PH SENSOR:

Since there was no pH sensor available in Wokwi, we needed to create a custom sensor to simulate a pH sensor. Figure 2 presents the code for the pH sensor.

```
#include "wokwi-api.h"
#include <stdio.h>
#include <stdlib.h>

typedef struct {
    pin_t pin;
    float pHValue;
} chip_data_t;

void chip_timer_callback(void *data) {
    chip_data_t *chip_data = (chip_data_t *)data;
    float pHValue = atan_read(chip_data->pHValue);
    float volts = 5 * (pHValue / 4896.0);
    pin_dac_write(chip_data->pin, volts);
}

void chip_init() {
    chip_data_t *chip_data = (chip_data_t *)malloc(sizeof(chip_data_t));
    chip_data->pHValue = atan_init("pHValue", 7);
    chip_data->pin = pin_init("OUT0", ANALOG);

    const timer_config_t config = {
        .callback = chip_timer_callback,
        .user_data = chip_data,
    };

    timer_t timer_id = timer_init(&config);
    timer_start(timer_id, 1000, true);
}
```

Figure 2 – pH Sensor Code.

E. COMPLETE INTEGRATION OF THE CIRCUIT:

After individual validation, the sensors were integrated into a single circuit, also simulated in Wokwi. The ESP-32 was programmed to collect data from all sensors simultaneously and send this information to the Blynk app in real time.

F. CREATION OF THE VIRTUAL DASHBOARD:

We created a dashboard in Blynk with widgets configured to display the real-time values of temperature, pH, oxygen level, and luminance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We tested the connection of the ESP-32 to the servo motor. The result obtained through programming was that while the servo motor does not receive a signal, it remains at 90 degrees, but when it receives the signal, the servo moves to 0 degrees. Next, we constructed the oxygen sensor in the simulation environment. The simulated sensor was SKU:SEN0237, based on [2]. For both the pH and oxygen sensors, it was necessary to build these sensors

in the simulator, based on other projects. This was because, although Wokwi provides a realistic simulation of electronic components, allowing the user to connect existing sensors in the tool to the hardware and write the code, neither the pH sensor nor the oxygen sensor is available in the simulator. In this context, we integrated the temperature sensor, the DS18B20, and the pH sensor along with the other components.

We also implemented a relay, as well as two LEDs. The relay simulates the command for a heating system, so when the temperature is below 24°C , the heating system is activated, and the LED connected to it lights up. The LED connected directly to the ESP-32 was a solution found to indicate when the light level is below 6000 lumens, serving as a warning signal.

It is worth noting that initially, the goal was to include a real-time clock (RTC) in the code, with functions based on this clock. This was intended because the goal was to feed the fish at 6 AM and 6 PM every day. However, every time we tried to implement the RTC in the program, it did not work. To resolve this, we removed the RTC, and the time began to be fetched from the internet via WiFi to feed the fish at those times, as shown in the code below:

```
void loop() {
    // Ativando o Blynk
    Blynk.run();

    struct tm tstruct;

    // Pega o horário
    getLocalTime(&tstruct);

    // Checa o horário do dia para alimentar o peixe
    char buffer[0]; // HH:MM:SS
    sprintf(buffer, "%02d:%02d:%02d", tstruct.tm_hour, tstruct.tm_min, tstruct.tm_sec);
    Serial.println("Horário: " + String(buffer));

    // Verifica o horário
    if ((tstruct.tm_hour == 6 || tstruct.tm_hour == 18) &&
        tstruct.tm_min == 0 && tstruct.tm_sec == 0) {
        alimenta = !alimenta; // Alterna o estado de alimentação
        delay(1000); // Atraso para evitar múltiplas ativações no mesmo segundo
    }
}
```

Figure 3 – Clock Code.

Implementing the lines of code to establish communication between the embedded system and the cloud, the project key in Blynk was connected using the same key in the system code. Throughout the work, several difficulties and limitations were observed in the communication between the simulator and the cloud, as well as in the program itself. It was noted that, due to the pH sensor, there was a need to set the update rate in the cloud to every 500 milliseconds to prevent it from becoming overloaded.

Figure 3 – Integrated Circuit;

Figure 4 – Monitoring by Blynk

The graph in Figure 4 presents the monitoring screen accessed via mobile phone, where it is possible to view data on Lighting, Temperature, and Oxygen (Luminosity, Temperature, and Oxygen – in Portuguese).

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that simulation is effective for remotely monitoring key aquarium parameters like pH, oxygen, temperature, and luminance. Wokwi and Blynk were viable tools for building and controlling the system, though some limitations, such as pH sensor integration and cloud connectivity, were noted. Future improvements should focus on sensor integration

and cloud stability to enhance reliability and enable real-world aquarium applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] JAVAID, M.; HALEEM, A.; SINGH, R. P.; SUMAN, R. Enhancing smart farming through the applications of agriculture 4.0 technologies. *International Journal of Intelligent Networks*, v. 3, p. 150-164, 2022.
- [2] (SKU: SEN0237). Disponível em: https://wiki.dfrobot.com/Gravity__Analog_Dissolved_Oxygen_Sensor_SKU_SEN0237. Acesso em: 10 out. 2024.
- [3] CARVALHO JUNIOR, A.; SILVA FILHO, J. I.; MARIO, M. C. A Study of Paraconsistent Artificial Neural Cell of Learning Applied as PAL2v Filter. *Latin America Transactions*, v. 16, n. 1, p. 202-209, jan. 2018.
- [4] CARVALHO JUNIOR, A. *Redes de Comunicação Industrial*, apostila da disciplina RCIA5 do Curso Superior de Tecnologia em Automação Industrial, IFSP Cubatão, ed. 6, 2017, 502pp, disponível em: <https://sites.google.com/view/prof-arnaldo/disciplinas/csai-rcia5-rica6>.
- [5] ROBOT, Df. Gravity_Analog Dissolved Oxygen Sensor SKU SEN0237. Disponível em: https://wiki.dfrobot.com/Gravity__Analog_Dissolved_Oxygen_Sensor_SKU_SEN0237.. Acesso em: 5 ago. 2024.
- [6] SERRANO, Tiago Medici. *Introdução ao Blynk App*. Disponível em: <https://embarcados.com.br/introducao-ao-blynk-app/>. Acesso em: 5 ago. 2024.
- [7] CARVALHO JUNIOR, A. *Proposta de Estimador de Qualidade de Enlace em Redes de Sensores Industriais Sem Fio Utilizando Rede Neural Artificial Paraconsistente*. 2017.113f. Dissertação (Mestrado Profissional em Engenharia Mecânica) – Universidade Santa Cecília, Santos, 2017.